

Influence of the family on the emergence of adolescent Victimism Behavior

Murzagulova Meiramkul

3rd year doctoral student of the specialty "8D01823 - Social Pedagogy and Self-Knowledge", Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Pedagogy, L. Gumilyov Eurasian National University. 0000-0002-1655-6252

Atemova Kalipa

Faculty of Social Sciences, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University 0000-0002-3864-1431

Konyrbayeva Sarash

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Faculty of philosophy and political science, 0000-0003-3497-990X

Turegeldiyeva Akzharkin

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, 0000-0002-8134-3392

Sagimbayeva Gulnaz

Director of the Department of scientific and methodical support and applied research of the National scientific and practical institute for children's wellbeing "Orken", 0009-0002-1848-5993

Mirzapeyssova Meruyert

2nd year PhD student, Master of pedagogical sciences, 8D01801 Doctoral student of the educational program "Social pedagogy", L.N. Gumilev Eurasian National University, 0009-0000-3614-3212

ABSTRACT: The psychological stability of children is affected by the situation in the family first of all. Upbringing process plays a significant role as psychological condition for happy childhood. Cruelty and rudeness in some families have a negative effect on the child's psychology and contribute to the child's shyness. The article examines the influence of family members, peers, schoolmates and teachers on the formation of a child in society.

Keywords: Family; Teachers; Teenagers; Education; Abuse, Environment, Upbringing.

Introduction

Literature Review

Methods

Discussion and results

Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

This article provides a detailed analysis of the impact of family violence on adolescents. In particular, it is assessed whether there are differences in the probability of multivictimization of adolescents who have experienced domestic violence and violence outside the home. The analysis is carried out on the basis of the data obtained during the study of teenagers of secondary schools in the city of Almaty.

Traditionally, the main institution of education is the family. What a child acquires in the family during childhood, he retains throughout his entire subsequent life. The family is considered as a social institution where the emotional, social and intellectual formation of personality mainly takes place. Studies of the characteristics of personality formation in

onto- and dysontogenesis by many authors: (1968, 1979); (1978); (); (1983); (1983); (1976, 2000); (1982); (1980, 1995); V. S. Mukhina (1999); (1989); (1998); (1990) and others - showed that the formation of personality, its emotional sphere, "I-concept", the specifics of relationships with other people depend on the attitude towards the child in the family. Criminologists pay great attention to the family in the development of personality. , considering the role of the family in the formation of an individual's morality, indicates that it is the moral and pedagogical inferiority of the family, manifested in an unhealthy moral and psychological atmosphere, rudeness, the wrong line of family education, antisocial functions, that leads to defective formation of the individual and, as a rule, to his criminality and victim behavior.

One of the main features of the modern approach to the role of the family in the development of personality is a shift in emphasis from the individual to the environment of interpersonal relationships. This allows us to consider a person as a participant in a large number of interpersonal relationships, and a family as a system that forms the most typical patterns of these relationships. In the structure of psychotraumatic relationships between an individual and a family, the emotional support of interpersonal relationships takes a central place. This is due to the importance of the place of emotion in the organization and integration of mental processes, as well as the interrelationship of the mental and somatic systems of the individual; it determines the range of emotions that usually accompany a traumatic experience, such as states of dissatisfaction, melancholy, depression, fear, anxiety, uncertainty, helplessness, anxiety, increased the emergence of internal conflict and excessive difficulties

Traumatic interpersonal relationships can arise at different time intervals in early and late childhood, as well as in the present. Usually their combined influence on the occurrence of violations takes place. A person's past experience remaining in the subconscious influences the perception of the present. Considering the family system in this paradigm, one can see what manifestations of family relationships, roles, structures and stereotypes of the family influence the formation of personality traits leading to victimization.

Results indicate that direct experience of family violence is associated with children's likelihood of being victimized outside the home. Finally, the implications of these results are discussed.

Relevance of the research topic. Domestic violence is a serious social problem that affects the physical and mental health of victims, especially adolescents. Young people are the future of society, and domestic violence has long-term and far-reaching effects on young people's physical and mental health, and may even affect their lifelong development.

From the definitions given to the family, "family is a small social group that experiences the main stages of a person's life"

Family is defined as "a small group based on marriage and blood kinship" in the explanation of the Kazakh language. A person is first born in a family and has relations with family members. The structure and form of the family has its influence on the development and socialization of a person.

2. Literature Review

The ideas of the Kazakh people about family traditions in raising children began with the works of Kazakh educators Y. Altynsarin, A. Kunanbayev, A. Baitursynov, M. Dulatov, M. Zhumabayev, Zh. Aymauytov and others. Abai paid attention to daily family upbringing and the specificity of parental responsibility in the education of young people.

Murzagulova's work "Factors of victimization in social pedagogy" reviews the works of scientists who have studied the factors of victimization and presents them in a table. It is concluded that general victimization factors are a set of conditions that cause this process. Including researchers K.I. Yurov and I.A. Yurov (2023) emphasize the influence of the family factor on the formation of victim behavior in adolescents.

With long-term and repeated strong stimulation of domestic violence, adolescents can gradually move from nervousness and anxiety to emotional indifference, causing resentment and even hatred for parents. Both of these conditions can lead to emotional disturbances in adolescents, cause conflicts and conflicts between parents and children, and in some cases can even lead to serious consequences for adolescents in the form of opposition or revenge against parents.

First, domestic violence harms the mental health of adolescents. Domestic violence is a terrible experience, so teenagers can feel negative emotions such as fear, helplessness, disappointment and hopelessness, which leave a deep mark on their psyche and even affect their emotional experience and social adjustment in the long term. Adolescents may experience deep depression, frequent mood swings, self-doubt, low self-esteem, and negative emotional disturbances such as fear (Sitkovsky A. L., Koimshidi G. F., 2021). In addition, conflicts between parents or relatives due to domestic violence can lead to family breakdown, which is more psychologically damaging to adolescents.

Second, domestic violence affects the social behavior and personal qualities of adolescents. Teenagers are very sensitive. When they are victims of domestic violence, they feel shy, insecure, unsteady, alienated from life. This, in turn, leads to the suspicion of the people around him, and contributes to the development of that teenager into a withdrawn and angry person who avoids social interaction.

As a result, the adolescent becomes resentful of life and has a negative impact on personal development. Also, all these events have a negative effect on the psychological state of the teenager and lead to sexual violence (Ignatov A.N., Soloviev V.S., 2021).

In addition, domestic violence affects the academic and professional development of adolescents. Young people affected by family violence suffer from physical and psychological problems. They often suffer from headaches, insomnia, falls, fear, and even decrease their motivation to study, which hinders their academic and professional development and causes them to lose hope and confidence in the future (Rudensky E.V. 2023)

We can see that the difficult situation in the family has a significant impact on the physical and psychological condition of the young generation. Family is the first environment where every child interacts and is formed, as well as the symbol of the school

education code. Parents should provide conditions for their children to grow up in a good environment. This is because such situation affects the psychology of each child and directly contributes to his becoming confident, persistent and responsible in the future (Lepeshev D. V., 2023).

The influence of the family on young people is very great, because psychologists said: the problem of society is in the person, and the problem of the person is in the early age, and the problem in the early age is in the family, if the quality of the parents is individual, as well as the way of family upbringing.

They have a great impact on a child's mental health as well as learning. Therefore, the unity in the family strongly influences the child's education, if the family is the biggest victim, the child will not have a sense of security, usually in the process of the child's growth, it is necessary to pay attention not only to the physical health, growth and development of the child, but also to the psychological formation.

Parents are the first teachers of their children, and when teenagers have not yet formed an independent personality, parents become the object of early imitation of the words and behavior of teenagers and constantly have a subtle influence on them. Family education has a direct, comprehensive and long-lasting effect on the mental health of adolescent students (A.S. Medvedeva, 2023).

In addition, among many family factors, a large negative impact on the mental health of adolescents can lead to poor relations between parents, and the negative impact on the mental health of children is mainly reflected in the following: children live in an environment full of contradictions, the demands of parents are always consistent does not come, there is no peace, peace and happiness in the family.

Adolescents are in a critical and unique period of physical and mental development, their psychology is not yet mature, their character is not yet defined, environment and stimuli can greatly influence their growth and development. Family, as one of the main environments in which young people grow up, definitely affects their healthy growth. Domestic violence is a very negative factor in the family environment that has a very negative effect on the physical and mental development of adolescents. Being a victim of domestic violence, adolescents experience not only physical pain, but also psychological injuries and distortions, as well as related problems (Murzagulova M. D., Shynbolat A. G., 2023).

1. Domestic violence greatly harms the mental health of adolescents

Parents are the first teachers in the upbringing of young people, a harmonious and good family makes young people appreciate the value of family love and increase their confidence in society. In some cases, domestic violence goes hand in hand with child abuse, which harms children who experience and suffer from domestic violence. Children who grow up in such a family, which is deeply affected by domestic violence, inevitably do a lot of damage by casting a gray, sad shadow, many of them suffer from fear, anxiety, loneliness, low self-esteem, anxiety about nobody and other psychological disorders.

2. Domestic violence can lead to physical destruction of young people

In today's society, people pay more attention to the importance of family education for the growth of young people. However, many families do not have proper parenting methods, or believe in the "convulsive dogma of child care" or cannot control their emotions, and if the child makes a mistake or fails to comply with their demands, the child is corporal punishment. Such wrong practice not only affects children's mental health, but also causes all sorts of harm to children and even causes lifelong regret.

3. Domestic violence can easily lead to juvenile delinquency.

If family members quarrel for several days and get used to violence to solve problems, then this makes the youth to form violent thoughts to solve problems, so they get used to violent aggression, because many parents have children and parents. used to accept rude and wild ways of education and formation of harsh opposition. Young people who grow up in families dealing with violent problems, with a characteristically rude and cold character, with psychological carelessness and cruelty, easily succumbing to impulses, poor self-control, bold and reckless, after these young people develop a criminal consciousness, the motive for crime is found, and violent crimes occur. . Most of them are aggressive.

Adolescents' perception of parental violence.

One of the most representative definitions of this type of domestic violence was proposed by the Canadian scientist Cottrell. Parental abuse is any behavior aimed at causing physical, psychological, or economic harm to a child's parents for the purpose of exerting power and control. Specifically, physical violence includes aggressive behavior such as pushing, hitting, spitting, kicking, and punching. Psychological abuse refers to emotional (eg threatening parents or even threats of suicide or leaving home) and verbal (eg yelling, insults, name-calling and belittling) behaviors that hurt parents. Economic violence includes behavior such as stealing, selling, destroying family or parental property, demanding that parents buy things they cannot afford, or incurring debts that parents must pay (Sitkovsky A. L., Koimshidi G. F., 2021).

Parental control and dominance manifests itself in placing unrealistic demands on parents (for example, requiring parents to quit their jobs to meet the child's demands) or in controlling household chores. This concept shows the various manifestations of violence against parents of adolescents, but does not indicate that the child is doing it on purpose.

The family context plays a crucial role in the development of conflict management skills. Positive and supportive relationships between parents and adolescents are known to promote independence in adolescents and allow them to express their views in times of conflict.

Conversely, negative and controlling parent-child interactions undermine the adolescent's autonomy and can create reactive and oppositional behaviors that contribute to new conflicts.

A favorable parenting climate based on support for adolescent autonomy and positive parental responsibility is associated with less conflict in child-parent relationships and positive resolution-based conflict management.

Research points to healthy family relationships as a major predictor of adolescent involvement in high-risk behaviors. Children who perceive their families as more cohesive and emotionally supportive are less likely to commit suicide and become sexually active earlier. Similarly, in the area of substance use, the important protective role of the family has been shown to mediate other predictors of substance use.

Many studies show that maladaptive and aggressive behavior in adolescents is associated with inappropriate educational experiences, ineffective parental control and guidance, and negative relationships between family members. In other words, the family can be a protective factor against the aggressive behavior of adolescents.

Adolescents who feel emotionally connected to their families are more confident and independent, and less prone to violence and antisocial behavior. Bullying behavior was associated with several family variables and parenting patterns, such as low parental involvement, strict and authoritarian parenting, conflict between parents, and high levels of parenting stress.

3. Methods

We conducted a brief survey of 100 residents of Almaty over 35 years of age. The question included "When you were a child/adolescent, were you abused by your parents or relatives (hit, denied food, kicked out of the house)

Figure 1. Age of respondents

According to the survey, 100 people, 40% from 35 to 50 years old, 20% from 50 to 65 years old, 25% from 65-75 years old, 15% from 75-85 years old. There is increasing evidence that it is associated with externalizing and internalizing behavior problems.

According to UNICEF 2022 data, 40% of children in Kazakhstan face violence at home. According to UNICEF research, children exposed to domestic violence and abuse not only suffer injuries, but can also experience developmental delays, mental health problems and depression.

Figure 2 . Victimization of children in Kazakhstan

Figure 3. Number of girls and boys in the study

Also, for the study, we chose three public schools in Almaty city, a sample was determined for students of grades 7-10. There were 60 people in the first school, 45 people in the second school, 55 people in the third school, total number of 160 people, 70 boys and 90 girls. The average age of schoolchildren is from 13 to 16 years

Peer victimization is also associated with parenting styles such as high levels of aggressive and reactive parenting, high levels of obsessive and irresponsible parental demands, and lack of cooperation in the parent-child relationship. In contrast, family cohesion is a protective variable for both bully and victim roles.

We also asked questions to Kazakhstanis aged 25-40. The number of those requested is 50 people. We ask "Are you happy and satisfied with your current life?" we asked a question.

Figure 4. Answers to the question

19 people answered "no", 11 people answered "yes", and 20 people answered "I don't know". According to the answers of those who took part in the survey, we see that 100%, 38% of people are dissatisfied with life.

We also asked 1) "Did you experience bullying at school or at home when you were a teenager?" we asked, the next question is 2) "Do you think that the appearance of victim behavior in your childhood is the reason why you are not happy now?"

Figure 5, Answers to question № 1

№ 1 "Were you abused at home when you were a teenager?" to the first question, 46% answered "yes", 20% answered "no", and the remaining 34% answered "don't know".

To question number 2, "Do you think that the appearance of victim behavior in your childhood is the reason why you are not happy now?"

46% answered "yes", 20% answered "no", and the remaining 34% answered "don't know".

4. Discussion and Results

The formation of relations between parents and children also affects the formation of children's future personality. Thus, research shows that adolescents whose parents support

their autonomy and refrain from using psychological control feel freer to explore and accept their sense of identity.

Conversely, parents who intrude on teenagers' inner thoughts and feelings and force them to think or act in a certain way can interfere with their ability to be in tune with their inner selves, making it difficult for them to make decisions based on their individuality.

Regarding school adjustment, research shows that adolescents from democratic-style families show better school adjustment, are more academically competent and school-oriented, engage in fewer episodes of bad behavior at school, and are more goal-oriented in both learning and performance.

As a result, although sometimes relationships with our teenage children can be difficult and frustrating for both parties, many studies show that family communication is a key factor in their adequate social-emotional development and successful coping with this period.

One of the main findings of this study is the existence of a direct and indirect relationship between family climate perceived as conflict by the adolescent and school victimization. Thus, a high-conflict family reduces adolescent personal resources such as self-esteem and increases the presence of depressive symptoms.

Perhaps, such a negative self-perception can lead adolescents to show submissive behavior and become vulnerable objects, easy prey for peer abuse, because, according to some authors, aggressors expect signs of suffering and submission from their victims.

Primary victimization is the direct experience of any illegal activity, that is, being a victim of a crime. Depending on the type of crime a person is a victim of, he may suffer physical, psychological, economic or other consequences. At the same time, in particular, the following factors are analyzed: the relationship between the offender and the victim, the effect of victimization cycles, power relations, the victim's perspective, feedback or the strengthening of the victim's circumstances. In addition, consider risk factors such as personal vulnerability (personal psycho-bio-social risks, lack of social skills, cultural differences, illiteracy, immaturity or disability), relational vulnerability (large power differential) or contextual vulnerability (powerlessness factor) and victim distress assessment. is necessary. Different studies talk about the trajectory of victimization. According to Finkelhor (1979), the accumulation of unfavorable factors leads to the growth of cruelty and injustice (Finkelhor D., Ormrod R., Turner H., Hamby S.L., 2005).

Family disadvantage, as one of the factors that determine criminal violence against minors, takes the leading place in terms of severity of victimogenic value. "The level of safety of children compared to representatives of other social groups is determined by the stability of the family as a social institution. The crisis in this sphere, the mutual alienation of people, not only sharply reduces the protective potential of family relations, but also often brings them directly to criminal responsibility, the victims of which are primarily members of the youth groups." . The comprehensiveness of the spectrum of situations that cause family discomfort requires its detailed consideration. Kazakh criminologists have introduced a special term "family socialization" to describe these processes.

Among the factors of victimization, the most important is the economic weakness associated with the inequality of different groups of the modern Kazakh society. "For sacrifice, the polarization of economic and social inequality of different groups of the population and commercial ideology as a measure of spiritual values should be recognized as important." The low material level of the family is directly related to the risk of victimization of its minor members.

The low income of families with children creates a number of problems that negatively affect their degree of protection from violent crimes against life and health. Being the main determinant of many negative social phenomena, financial disadvantage affects the ability of parents to pay enough attention to the issues of raising children, control their location and properly ensure their safety. The daily life of the family requires an increase in the employment of parents, which leaves the problems of organizing the free time of minors. In such a situation, children often become hostages of aimless entertainment, surrounded by dubious people, which contributes to their victimization. The situation is even more difficult in single-parent families, where the absence of one of the parents, in light of the need to perform the function of material support, has a negative impact on the task of raising the child.

5. Conclusion

The President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev has signed the law on strengthening responsibility for domestic violence. The newly adopted law strengthened the responsibility of society and every citizen. Domestic violence is a global problem, whether it exists to some extent in developed or developing countries. Starting from the phenomenon of domestic violence, which is widespread nowadays, the article states that family violence easily affects the environment of young people, poses serious violations and threats to their physical and mental health, and even leads them to delinquency, which is contrary to the development of a harmonious society. Therefore, in order to reduce the spread of such a phenomenon as domestic violence, it is necessary to create a system of social support as soon as possible at the moral, legal, social and caring levels.

To conclude we want to point out that the modern concept of preventing victimized behavior involves a complex of medical-psychological, psychological-pedagogical and socio-legal assistance and support for families and children at social risk through the implementation of social rehabilitation and correction programs for children and adolescents with deviations in mental and social development. International experience shows that the implementation of preventive measures and programs has certain general trends and principles:

- professionalization of educational, preventive and security activities;
- creation of a network of special preventive services and structures designed to provide social and socio-psychological assistance to families, children, and youth (psychological services and consultations, trust centers, leisure and rehabilitation centers, social shelters for children and adolescents in critical situations);

- recognition of the family as the leading institution for the socialization of children and adolescents, implementation of special measures of socio-legal, socio-pedagogical and medical-psychological assistance to the family, primarily to families that cannot cope with the tasks of education on their own;
- psychologization of educational, preventive and protective activities, the leading role of medical and psychological assistance and support in the correction of victim behavior of children and adolescents, rehabilitation of minors with various forms of social and mental maladjustment.

Taking into account these principles, preventive work should be built aimed at preventing and correcting the victim behavior of a teenager. In the light of recent research, the emphasis on the institution of fatherhood, which has been practically destroyed in our society, as the basis for the healthy development of a child's personality and the formation of safe behavior patterns in him, becomes significant. The style of parental education itself should be based on the positions of psychology and pedagogy of non-violence as the leading form of organizing interpersonal family relationships.

6. References

1. Medvedeva A. S. (2023) Victimization of minors in the process of cybergrooming: gender and psychosexual specifics //Psychology and Law.- Vol. 13. – no. 4. – p 83-94.
2. Sitkovsky A. L., Koimshidi G. F.(2021) Characteristics of criminal victimization of the elderly and minors, as well as expected trends in its development until 2023 //Akademicheskaya mysl. - No. 4 (17). - p 124-133.
3. Ignatov A. N., Soloviev V. S. (2023) Information and cognitive technologies in the mechanism of digital victimization // Herald of the Kazan legal institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. - Vol. 14. – no. 1 (51). - p. 59-66.
4. Lepeshev D. V. etc.(2023) JESTOKOE OBRASCHENIE S DETMI I PODROSTKAMI V SEMYE AS A WORLD PROBLEM //Наука и реальность/Science&Reality. - No. 4 (16). – p. 19-23.
5. Rakhimova G.(2023) PROBLEMS OF LEGAL REGULATION OF THE PROTECTION OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM //VESTNIK KAZNPU IMENI ABAYA, SERIES "HISTORICAL AND SOCIAL-POLITICAL SCIENCES". - Vol. 3. – no. 78.
6. Murzagulova M. D., Shynbolat A. G. (2023) THE WORK OF A SOCIAL EDUCATOR WITH ADOLESCENTS WITH VICTIMIZED BEHAVIOR //Prevention of bullying and cyberbullying in educational organizations: theory and practice. p. 131-134.
7. Finkelhor D., Ormrod R., Turner H., Hamby S.L. (2005) The victimization of children and youth: A comprehensive, national survey. Child Maltreatment. ;10:5–25. doi: 10.1177/1077559504271287.
8. M.D. Murzagulova,, K.T.Atemova,, D.A. Zhunusova , (2023) Factors of victimization in social pedagogy(/ No. 4(145)/2023/ NEWSLETTER of Eurasian National University named after L.N. Gumilev Pedagogy. Psychology. Sociology series-162 pages.
9. Rudensky E.V. (2023) Deprivation victimism as a socio-psychological mechanism of ontogenesis of personal victimization // World of science, culture, education. No. 1(38). P.139-144.